

THE IMPORTANCE OF BOOK READING IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: *The following are some suggestions on how to read a book, and some tips and suggestions for readers.*

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Recognized today as the eighth miracle, the book is a magical lamp that illuminates the human heart, purifies the soul, illuminates distant and dark ways of life. At the same time, the art of public speaking is important for the bright future of every young person who is brought up in the spirit of a new worldview.

It is important to note that before embarking on a journey into the world of books and learning the secrets of oratory, the reader is naturally asked, "Who is a reader? What is oratory? Where does reading begin? What is the secret of a great orator?" First of all, a real reader can live with it when he reads this book, be happy on happy days, be genuinely sad when he is sad, analyze the events, draw the right conclusions for himself, and live in them. is a person who tries to use settings for their intended purpose. So where does reading begin? to which I answer without hesitation from the family.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev said: "Many people, unfortunately, do not know how to read a book, and many do not understand why they are reading". Some see this as a difficult but the only way to become literate. According to them, any book can make a person "educated". For others, reading is a pastime, a pastime, and what to read to them (articles, novels, poems, messages, etc.) is not boring. A reader who simply wants to relax, spend time, and be "educated" will feel an unknown power in the book that purifies the tongue and inspires the person. However, he cannot clearly imagine or evaluate this power. Such a reader is like a patient who is completely ignorant of medicine, that is, he begins to taste each box without understanding exactly what medicine he needs. In fact, when it comes to reading, isn't it good that everyone can find only the books they need, that can give them new strength and inspiration?

Of course, we authors like people to read a lot. It is not correct for the author to focus on the fact that readers read too many books. Because ten good readers are better than a thousand indifferent readers. Therefore, I can easily say that it is read too much everywhere, and it is not a reputation for literature, but a detriment. The book is not written to further weaken those who are not independent, but is sometimes used to show the disabled a cheap and easy-to-change landscape. Books are useful only when they guide a person to life and serve him. If the book does not give the reader, even if a little, energy, courage, and spiritual purity, every hour spent reading it will be in vain.

Reading a book nourishes a person spiritually, enriches his heart. The light of enlightenment, called goodness, shines in the heart of one who loves to read. It is no coincidence that Anton Pavlovich Chekhov, a great figure in Russian literature, did not say, "Everything is light in the face of books." I am heartbroken to see passengers who do not want to close the pages of their book despite the congestion and inconvenience when using public transport such as the subway and bus. I am convinced that there are still people among us who dedicate the golden hours of their lives to books. Especially at a time when many lessons in the life of the XXI century are carried out by technology, computers, modern young people are becoming friends with books, which gives hope for a bright future for our country.

They think that reading a book expands his worldview, it is necessary to read the book and understand its essence. Reading a book alone is not the end of the story. The number of books read does not determine our culture, but the number of culture-understood books. At the end of our lives, the number of books read is not asked. In order to live a good life, we need to read a book based on the right choice. Of course, it is necessary to read a book in order not to get lost in the way of life, to correctly distinguish between halal and haram, white and black. Unfortunately, many do not realize this yet.

A person who reads a book lives thousands of lives before he dies. A person who has never read a book experiences only one experience. is deception. First of all, it is necessary to start reading the book with small stories, if you read for 15-30 minutes every day, then, according to the purpose, then the reading time is gradually extended. Of course, it is necessary to read the works of Uzbek literature. If the book does not give the reader, albeit a little, energy, courage, spiritual purity, every hour spent reading will be in vain and useless. It is necessary to take spiritual nourishment from each book, to draw conclusions from the work.

Reading without thinking means blindfolded in the beauty of nature. We should read not to forget ourselves and our lives, but to understand the reins of life more consciously. It is necessary to approach the hunter not as a cowardly student, but as an aggressive climber ready to climb the highest peak.

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